

TEACHERS AND STUDENTS RELATIONSHIPS

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Here are some Teacher's quotes to celebrate the best teachers in our lives:

Dan Rather

The dream begins with a teacher who believes in you, who tugs and pushes and leads you to the next plateau, sometimes poking you with a sharp stick called truth

Henry Brooks Adams

A teacher affects eternity; he can never tell where his influence stops.

Robert Brault

The average teacher explains complexity; the gifted teacher reveals simplicity.

Cicero

The authority of those who teach is often an obstacle to those who want to learn.

Jacques Barzun

In teaching, you cannot see the fruit of a day's work. It is invisible and remains so, maybe for twenty years.

Helen Caldicott

Teachers, I believe, are the most responsible and important members of society because their professional efforts affect the fate of the earth.

Albert Einstein

It is the supreme art of the teacher to awaken joy in creative expression and knowledge.

Nikos Kazantzakis

Ideal teachers are those who use themselves as bridges over which they invite their students to cross, then having facilitated their crossing, joyfully collapse, encouraging them to create bridges of their own.

Johann Wolfgang von Goethe

A teacher who can arouse a feeling for one single good action, for one single good poem, accomplishes more than he who fills our memory with rows and rows of natural objects, classified with name and form.

Ken Blanchard

Your role as a leader is even more important than you might imagine. You have the power to help people become winners.

William Butler Yeats

Education is not the filling of a pail but the lighting of a fire.

Forest Witchcraft

A hundred years from now, it will not matter what kind of car I drove, what kind of house I lived in, how much money I had in the bank, but the world may be a better place because I made a difference in the life of a child.

Introduction

How many teachers take the time to connect with students on a personal level? How do you find the time, anyway? Teachers who manage to transcend the normal student-teacher relationships can benefit everyone in school or College --particularly the challenging students-- and, along the way, prevent violence, support safety, improve the climate, and promote learning. This is in a time of an increasingly rigid zero tolerance of the slightest hint of violence.

Both the teachers and administrators need to alter their own attitudes and behavior, they must learn to listen to students and accommodate their needs. The end result will be lasting relationships that can foster deeper understanding and growth for educators and students alike. In this article, you will discover ways to stay optimistic and persistent and see your students as having something to teach you.

This article would be useful for teachers, future teachers, and teacher educators, in the hope that it will be useful to them as they consider how students and teachers together construct their lives in classrooms.

This article reflects my understanding and interpretation of power relations as I observed them. It is centered on a constructivist view of power relations, not as brought into classrooms from the outside world, by the teacher or anyone else, but as created inside classrooms through the actions of teachers and students that take place every day.

Education is the key to success in life and teachers make a lasting impact in the lives of their students. Teaching is the greatest test of optimism. Great teachers focus not on compliance, but on connections and relationships. It is the little conversations that build the relationships and make an impact on each student. The best teacher teaches from the heart-not from the text book. The day you are willing to veer off the Lesson plan, follow a student's lead and learn with your students is the day you really become a Teacher! Those who learn more than they

can teach are the best Teachers of all. They don't care how you know until they know how much you care. The teacher's goal is simple-- to help the students reach theirs.

Teachers Play a Tough Balancing Act

I love working with the students of today. I call my students "my children" because in our time together they are not just names on the Attendance list, they become a part of my heart. Their energy and enthusiasm is contagious, and working with them truly does help to keep me young. I am certain that I learn as much from them as they do from me. Older generations are notorious for complaining about younger generations: "In my day we never would have . . ." But I must compliment this generation for being so accomplished, for their ability to multitask and to adapt to new technologies. I am impressed.

To me, this generation of students is different for one primary reason: Technology. The technological advances of the past several years have been substantial. Today's students grew up with the Internet, computers and cell phones prevalent in all aspects of their lives. They embrace new technologies and adapt faster than their predecessors.

In a classroom full of students with different learning abilities, the teacher faces a formidable challenge -- how to teach each child to his or her maximum potential. While some children in the class may find the lesson too mundane or boring, if it is "dumbed down," other children may find it difficult to cope with difficult concepts. So how does a teacher teach at an optimum level, such that both sets of extreme learning abilities are nurtured?

Who Is a Good Teacher?

A good teacher plays the role of an educator, guide, inspirational guru, and a friend. While gently nudging the 'slow learners' to climb the steep learning curve, he/she engages with the 'bright minds' to delve deeper into concepts and thereby meet their need to be ahead of others.

Teachers tap the fertile mind of young children and plant the seed of curiosity in them. This inculcates the values of self-learning, exploration, and philosophical inquiry. I have seen many young children who took the spark of imagination to unimaginable heights. I have known little enthusiasts to grow up to become engineers of cutting edge technology. I have met kids suffering from dyslexia who grew up and became famous surgeons. Who, other than a great teacher, could have been instrumental in this phenomenal rise?

The teachers should not try to fix students, they should fix themselves first. The good teacher makes the poor student good and the good student superior. When our students fail, we as teachers too have failed. Why should a student show an interest in our classes if we do not show an interest in them? Show them you care. Student relationships must come first.

Relationships with students extend far beyond the class rooms. The strength of our student relationships makes the difference in translating our passion for teaching into their passion for learning.

Teachers and Students Relationships

The present day Students are nothing if not impressive. The admissions requirements have become so stringent that every student is quite accomplished, not only in terms of academics but also in terms of athletics, performing arts and humanitarian efforts. So accomplished, in fact, that some faculty members, including me, sometimes wonder how we are teaching at the University that would not have admitted us.

While some students are the best and brightest in this country, they still deal with the same issues of transitioning to a college environment and managing their time among all the opportunities and distractions. Sometimes Faculty members forget that just because the students are accomplished does not mean that they aren't struggling with various choices.

Speaking of choices, the college years have been referred to as a time of emerging adulthood and a time of both exploration and commitment. As educators we need to encourage exploration as a means of helping students to make independent decisions for the future, to make a commitment. We hope they will develop these abilities during their time with us. They are the future leaders of this country, and we want to encourage and enable their passion and ingenuity.

The teacher needs to understand that in many schools and colleges, especially in big cities like New Delhi, Mumbai, Kolkata, Bangalore, etc. children come from different cultures and backgrounds. A teacher then needs to understand the value of the students' senses of belonging, which can be of greater value and build self worth for minority students as well as students from diverse states such as the North Eastern states, Bihar, Orissa, Kerala, Andhra Pradesh, etc.. If the teacher demonstrates an understanding of the student's culture, it will provide a better understanding between the teacher and the student.

Therefore, those teachers who demonstrate respect towards their students, automatically win favor by having active learners in their classroom. The arrogant or offensive teacher will lack these positive qualities due to his or her lack of control over the children. Teachers should assert that they should also be treated with respect and one of their key their responsibilities is to ensure that students treat each other with kindness.

Why are Teachers and Students Relationships important?

Student Teacher relationships are very important. When I was researching about Student teacher relationships and Student learning outcomes, the questions how do Student Teacher

relationships have an impact on Student learning outcomes emerged. Research has found that there is a link between Student Teacher relationships and Student learning outcomes.

Students that have positive relationships with their teachers have been found to be highly motivated, focused on their task, and have greater overall learning outcomes. The strength of our student relationships makes the difference in translating our passion for teaching into their passion for learning.

Therefore, how does a teacher hold a relationship that leads to effectively teach the children? The answer becomes clear when teachers interact with, and learn more about their students. Our first educational experience, which takes place in the primary years of our life, sets the principles for our future education. Every school or college year a teacher deals with new faces and new attitudes. Some children find themselves lacking an interest in learning and others feel playing and fooling around at school or college with friends is the happiest moment of their life. The solution to inappropriate behavior will not automatically get rid of the poor attitude of these children, but is to establish a positive relationship.

Teachers can establish a positive relationship with their students by communicating with them and properly providing feedback to them. Respect between teacher and student increases with both feeling enthusiastic when learning and teaching. Having established a positive relationship with students will encourage students to seek education and be enthusiastic and to be regular in attending school. Remembering our favorite teacher will be recognized because they had at least in one way or another the qualities I have discussed in this article. Although we are not aware of it during the time we are in school, but the teachers are well recognized at a later time of our lives.

You Owe Your Success to Your Teachers

All that I have achieved in my life is because of my teachers. Some of them were formally designated as my teachers -- in School, College, and University. Others, such as my parents, were my teachers nonetheless.

TO CONCLUDE...There are 5 things that students expect from their teachers:

1. Moments of wonder
2. Understanding of their world
3. Mutual trust
4. A bit of humour
5. A lively environment

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